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REWARD AND RECOGNITION PROGRAMS ON EMPLOYEE'S MOTIVATION: A STUDY ON STAR TV INDIA LTD

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Abstract

This study highlighted the reward and recognition programs on employee's motivation. The study was conducted for the 80 employees of STAR TV India Ltd. The data was collected by structured questionnaires. The factors affecting satisfaction were identified; payment (0.86**), promotion (0.74**), working condition (0.61**), personal(0.37*) as Analysis showed immense support for positive relationship between reward and employee satisfaction. All these results are statistically significant thus providing rigor and generalizability in research. This exploratory study suggests for the positive relationship between reward and satisfaction. In a competitive business climate, more business owners are looking at improvements in quality while reducing costs. Meanwhile, a strong economy has resulted in a tight job market. So while small businesses need to get more from their employees, their employees are looking for more out of them. Employee reward and recognition programs are one method of motivating employees to change work habits and key behaviors to benefit an organization.

Key Words: Reward, Recognitions, Motivation, Satisfaction and development.

1. INTRODUCTION

In order for an organization to meet its obligations to shareholders, employees and society, its top management must develop a relationship between the organization and employees that will fulfill the continually changing needs of both parties. At a minimum the organization expects employees to perform reliably the tasks assigned to them and at the standards set for them, and to follow the rules that have been established to govern the workplace. Management often expects

more: that employees take initiative, supervise themselves, continue to learn new skills, and be responsive to business needs. At a minimum, employees expect their organization to provide fair pay, safe working conditions, and fair treatment. (Beer, Spector, Lawrence, Mills, & Walton, 1984). Traditionally most reward and recognition programmes were vague and often given in response to a manager's perception of when an employee performed exceptionally well. There were usually no set standards by which exceptional performance could be measured, and it could have meant anything from having a good attitude, assisting another department, or being consistently punctual. In current organizational settings this is no longer the case, as organizations understand the great gains derived by linking rewards and recognition to their business strategy (Flynn, 1998) . In designing a reward program, a small business owner needs to separate the salary or merit pay system from the reward system. Financial rewards, especially those given on a regular basis such as bonuses, profit sharing, etc., should be tied to an employee's or a group's accomplishments and should be considered "pay at risk" in order to distance them from salary. By doing so, a manager can avoid a sense of entitlement on the part of the employee and ensure that the reward emphasizes excellence or achievement rather than basic competency.

Merit pay increases, then, are not part of an employee reward system. Normally, they are an increase for inflation with additional percentages separating employees by competency. They are not particularly motivating since the distinction that is usually made between a good employee and an average one is relatively small. In addition, they increase the fixed costs of a company as opposed to variable pay increases, such as bonuses, which have to be "re-earned" each year. Finally, in many small businesses teamwork is a crucial element of a successful employee's job. Merit increases generally review an individual's job performance, without adequately taking into account the performance within the context of the group or business.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

There is a large body of literature, including research literature, on rewards and recognition programmes. Many of the studies focus on the effects of rewards on task interest and performance and are found in the literature concerned with motivation: both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. In intrinsically motivated behavior there is no reward except with the task itself. Reward and recognition programmes come within the discussion on extrinsically

motivated behavior that occurs when an activity is rewarded by incentives not inherent in the task (Deci, 1971). Many contemporary authors have also defined the concept of motivation. Motivation has been defined as: the psychological process that gives behavior purpose and direction (Kreitner, 1995); a tendency to behave in a purposive method to achieve specific, unmet desires (Buford, Bedeian, & Lindner, 1995); an inner force to gratify an unsatisfied need (Higgins, 1994); and the will to accomplish (Bedeian, 1993). For this paper, motivation is operationally defined as the inner force that drives individuals to achieve personal and organizational goals.

Understanding what motivates employees is one of the key challenges for managers. Although it is not possible directly to motivate others, it is nonetheless important to know how to influence what others are motivated to do, with the overall aim of having employees identify their own welfare with that of the organization (Bruce and Pepitone, 1999). In general terms rewards programmes come within the overall concept of compensation strategies which are defined as the “deliberate utilization of the pay system as an essential integrating mechanism through which the efforts of various sub-units or individuals are directed towards the achievement of an organization’s strategic objectives” (Gomez-Mejia and Balkin, 1992). They are management tools that hopefully contribute to a firm's effectiveness by influencing individual or group behavior (Lawler and Cohen, 1992). All businesses use pay, promotion, bonuses or other types of rewards to encourage high levels of performance (Cameron and Pierce, 1977).

At a minimum, employees expect the organization to provide fair pay, safe working conditions, and fair treatment. Like management, employees often expect more, depending on the strength of their needs for security, status, involvement, challenge, power, and responsibility. Just how ambitious the expectations of each party are vary from organization to organization. For organizations to address these expectations an understanding of employee motivation is required (Beer et al., 1984). Carnegie (1975) emphasizes the human aspects of management. They postulate that as it is people who make a business succeed or fail it is the organization’s chief responsibility to motivate their people so that they will assure success. The authors believe that each human being has the potential for creativity and for achieving goals. The infinite question is how organizations reach this potential and how they stimulate creativity and foster in their

people the desire to succeed and to achieve self-fulfillment through their work. The common theme of the above authors is the belief that people need to be respected and treated as precious human capital, more essential to an organization's effectiveness than its financial capital. People are now seen as the primary source of a company's competitive advantage. Therefore, the way people are treated increasingly determines whether an organization will prosper or even survive (Lawler, 2003). Organizations are under constant pressure to enhance and improve their performance and are realizing that an interdependent relationship exists between organizational performance and employee performance. In the following section the focus will be on the motivational theories and the impact that these theories have on enhancing employee performance.

Garfield (1992) believed that if an employee recognition program was going to make a significant impact, it must be imbedded in the culture of the organization. He felt that in order for a program to become a part of the culture of the organization it must first be accepted by the employees, and then be promoted by management. Once a program becomes a normal part of the daily routine it will become effective. Another success factor was that recognition must be constantly given to employees, on a daily basis. A senior editor of *Training Magazine* said, "Recognition is something a manager should be doing all the time - it's a running dialogue with your people." (Nelson, 1994) noted that the best motivation comes from daily positive reinforcement by management of desired performance.

It is important to point out that daily recognition does not involve tangible awards. A simple verbal acknowledgment that the employee is performing well or a smile given by a supervisor is a meaningful approval of the employee's performance.

Honesty and timing are important parts of employee recognition. Canter believes that recognition must be given in a personal and honest manner. (Nelson, 1994) If it is not, it degrades the value of the recognition and the program will lose its credibility. The timing of the recognition and the type of recognition are also significant. If recognition is given too far after the achievement, its impact is diminished. (Nelson, 1994) Therefore, it is beneficial to recognize the desired behavior as soon as possible. The employee must also value the type of recognition. Niemes (1996) suggests that one tip for effective recognition program is to have a "family of rewards". A different type of recognition will motivate each person. It is important that when recognition is

given, the type of recognition will have meaning to that employee. Knowing what the employee values as recognition will keep the program a success. Thus, developing a “family”, in other words a variety, of awards that appeal to the needs of the employees is a factor in the success of a recognition program. (Niemes, 1996) The final factor of a successful employee recognition program is the act of recognizing recognition. (Nelson, date unknown) Simply speaking, a recognition program will not work if employees don’t get recognized. Therefore, the best way to ensure that employees obtain the recognition they deserve is to acknowledge the people who recognize the employee. Recognizing recognition is similar to a pep rally for the program. If you keep the idea of recognition in the thoughts of more people, the more it naturally becomes part of the culture of the organization.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND DATA COLLECTION:

The sample study used tells the variability and reliability of the biographical data of the respondents. The procedure used to gather data is the hypotheses and the statistical techniques used to analyze the data

Data Collection:

For the purpose of this study a quantitative methodology was followed and a questionnaire was used as the measuring instrument. The data gathering techniques used included a biographical questionnaire and the Work Satisfaction and Motivation Questionnaire as set out by De Beer (1987). “Reliability refers to the consistency or dependability of a measuring instrument. Validity, on the other hand, refers to the extent to which a measurement procedure actually measures what it is intended to measure rather than measuring something else, or nothing at all” (Leary, 2004, p. 69). De Beer (1987) conducted an item analysis to evaluate the inter-item consistency of the Work Motivation and Satisfaction. This provides an indication of the consistency of responses to all the items delineated in a measuring instrument. The Cronbach-Alpha reliability coefficients for the subsections of the Work Satisfaction and Motivation are as follows: Work content ($r = 0.78$), payment ($r = 0.86$), promotion ($r = 0.84$), recognition ($r =$

0.90), working conditions ($r = 0.77$), benefits ($r = 0.84$), my leader/supervisor ($r = 0.72$), general ($r = 0.75$). Prinsloo (1996) determined the internal consistency of the Work Motivation and Satisfaction Questionnaire by computing the coefficient alphas, conducting an item analysis and factor analysis. Prinsloo (1996) reported a coefficient alpha that is consistently high, ranging from .82 to .93, with a median of .90 for the instrument. The results of the item analysis also indicated that each item had a positive correlation with the total score for the Work Motivation and Satisfaction Questionnaire, with the average correlations ranging from a low of .42 to .74, with a median correlation of .64. This suggests that the 43 items of the Work Motivation and Satisfaction Questionnaire are relatively homogenous with respect to the underlying attitude construct they measure (Prinsloo, 1996). According to Prinsloo (1996), the reliability of this instrument is determined with SPSS. The calculated coefficient-alpha is 0.82, which suggests a strong positive item-homogeneity in this measuring instrument. This signifies as an indication of test reliability.

The questionnaire consisted of nine dimensions that impact employee satisfaction and motivation.. The Nine Dimensions of the Questionnaire are as follows:

1. Work content probed the respondents' feelings about the type of work they do.
2. Payment probed respondents' satisfaction with their salaries.
3. Promotion probed for the opportunity that the organization offers for promotion.
4. Recognition probed whether the respondent was receiving the recognition and feedback for the jobs they perform.
5. Working conditions were probed as the fifth factor and looked at opportunity to mix with colleagues and interpersonal relations.
6. Benefits looked at whether the benefits such as pension, medical schemes and leave were satisfactory.
7. Personal probed the respondents' feelings towards their job.
8. Leadership or supervision probed the level of satisfaction with the manager.

9. General probed if the respondents' had considered alternative employment, and hence their level of satisfaction with the organization.

Procedure and Statistical Methods

80 questionnaires were distributed among the employees out of whom 65 were responded appropriately giving an 85% response which is acceptable to make this study rigorous and generalizable. The obtained data is analyzed through SPSS. The statistical methods involved those of descriptive (mean and standard deviation) and inferential statistics (Pearson Correlation) for the predictors of motivation and satisfaction of employees.

4. RESULTS ANALYSIS OF DATA:

1) Table 1: Descriptive statistics for the dimensions of work motivation and satisfaction

Sl.no	Variables	Mean	SD(standard deviation)
1	Work Content	1.53	.69
2	Payment	2.57	.65
3	Promotion	2.10	.62
4	Recognition	2.88	.62
5	Working Conditions	1.34	.72
6	Benefits	1.86	.63
7	Personal	1.23	.64
8	Leader/Supervisor	1.42	.69
9	General	1.32	.54

Interpretation: After analyzing the table no-1 Where high variables correspond to high motivation With respect to the dimensions of work motivation assessed by the work motivation and satisfaction questionnaire, Table 1 indicates that the means for the work content, payment, promotion, recognition, working conditions, benefits, personal, leader/supervisor and general ranged from a low of 1.32 to a high of 2.88. It therefore appears that staff in the sample is relatively motivated however, the mean values for payment, promotion, recognition and benefits were the lowest. These mean values indicate the areas that employees were most likely to be demotivated and dissatisfied Table 1 thus shows that staff in the sample is most likely to be motivated due to their working conditions, personal and general dimensions. They are least motivated by the payment they receive and recognition as determined by the

2) Table 2: Dimension Correlations rewards and satisfaction of Work Motivation and Satisfaction

Table no-2

Sl.no	Variables	Pearson correlation	Variable Significance (2-tailed)
1	Work Content	0.66**	0.000
2	Payment	0.86**	0.000
3	Promotion	0.74**	0.000
4	Recognition	0.92**	0.000
5	Working Conditions	0.61**	0.000
6	Benefits	0.65*	0.000
7	Personal	0.37*	0.000
8	Leader/Supervisor	0.32*	0.023
9	General	0.34*	0.005

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Interpretation: After analyzing the data the results indicate that work content correlates significantly with work motivation and satisfaction ($r = 0.66, p < 0.01$). This supports the hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between work content and work motivation and satisfaction. A significant correlation is shown to exist between payment and work motivation and satisfaction ($r = 0.86, p < 0.01$), supporting the hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between payment and work motivation and satisfaction. There was also a significant relationship between promotion and work motivation and satisfaction ($r = 0.74, p < 0.01$). Hence, this supports the hypothesis that promotion opportunities are significantly related to work motivation and satisfaction.

A significant correlation also exists between recognition and work motivation and satisfaction ($r = 0.92, p < 0.01$), supporting that recognition is significant in explaining the variance in work motivation and satisfaction. There was a significant relationship between working conditions and work motivation and satisfaction ($r = 0.61, p < 0.01$). Hence, the hypothesis that there is a relationship between working conditions and work motivation and satisfaction is supported. There was a significant relationship between benefits and work motivation and satisfaction ($r = 0.65, p < 0.01$), supporting the hypothesis that benefits are significant in explaining work motivation and satisfaction.

A significant correlation was found to exist between the dimension of personal and work motivation and satisfaction ($r = 0.37, p < 0.05$). There was a significant relationship between leader/supervisor and work motivation and satisfaction ($r = 0.32, p < 0.05$) as well as between general and work motivation and satisfaction ($r = 0.34, p < 0.05$). The results indicate that for the Intercorrelation matrix exploring the relationship between the dimensions of the Work Satisfaction and Motivation Questionnaire, that all the coefficients were positive. The results depicted in Table indicate that there is a significant statistical relationship between the dimensions of work motivation and satisfaction. Accordingly, the null hypothesis is rejected.

3) Table 3 The relationship between rewards, recognition and work motivation and Satisfaction.

Table no-3

items	Work satisfaction and Motivation
Reward	0.86**
Recognition	0.92**

**** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)**

Interpretation : After analyzing the data and table no-3, There is a statistically significant, direct and positive relationship between rewards and work satisfaction and motivation ($r = 0.86$, $p < 0.01$). Hence, if rewards offered to employees were to be altered, then there would be a corresponding change in work motivation and satisfaction. The coefficient of determination, ($R - \text{squared} = 0.74$), implies that 74% of the variation in work motivation and satisfaction of the sample can be attributed to rewards received, which implies that the remaining 26% can be explained by other factors not considered. The results indicate that there is a statistically significant, direct and positive relationship between recognition and work satisfaction and motivation ($r = 0.92$, $p < 0.01$). This implies that if the recognition accorded to employees were to change, there would be a change in work motivation and satisfaction. The coefficient of determination, ($R - \text{squared} = 0.60$), implies that 60% of the variation in work motivation and satisfaction of the sample can be attributed to recognition, while the remaining 40% can be attributed to other variables which were not explored in the current research.

4. Multiple Regression Analysis

On the basis of the results obtained indicating a direct positive relationship between the dimensions of work satisfaction and motivation, all the dimensions of the instrument were assessed using multiple regression analysis to ascertain the extent to which they explain the variance in work satisfaction and motivation.

Table 4: Stepwise Regression: Dependent variable (work motivation and satisfaction)

Multiple Regression		0.93942		
R squared (R ²)		0.84276		
R squared (Adjusted R ²)		0.71404		
Standard error		3.43232	F = 16.59	Sig. F = 0.00**
Variables in the equation	B	SE for B	T	P
Work Content	-2.9645	1.1857	2.36	0.03*
Payment	-1.5234	0.2863	5.32	0.00**
Promotion	-0.6828	0.2903	3.65	0.00**
Recognition	-2.6846	1.1857	2.48	0.00**
Working Conditions	-1.2534	0.2863	1.34	0.00**
Benefits	-0.5856	0.2903	1.65	0.00**
Personal	-3.5535	0.1452	1.79	0.00**
Leader/Supervisor	-2.2338	1.7683	1.43	0.00**
General	-2.1045	0.1564	1.33	0.00**

Table no-4

Interpretation :The results shown in Table 4 indicate a relatively high percentage of the variation in work motivation and satisfaction can be explained by the variables entered in the equation (R - squared = 84.27%; R- squared (adjusted) = 71.4%). Thus 71% of the variance in work motivation and satisfaction can be explained by work content, payment, promotion, recognition, working conditions, benefits, personal, leader/supervisor and general dimensions. The F-ratio of 16.59 (p < 0.01) indicates the regression of work motivation and satisfaction on the dimensions assessed, expressed through the adjusted squared multiple (R - squared (adj.) = 71.40%) is statistically significant. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. These variables account for 71% of the variance in work motivation and satisfaction. This finding suggests that other unexplored variables could account for the other variance in work motivation and satisfaction.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR STAR TV

The reward and recognition recommendations for STAR TV India Ltd.

Sl.no	REWARD NAME	WHAT	WHO	WHEN	HOW	AWARD VALUE
1	Employee of the month	Award given to employee	Staff, team heads	Monthly	On the basis of special contribution to the organization, responsible attitude toward his/her job	Employees are recognized during monthly staff meetings with a plaque or certificate
2	Innovator award	Award given for innovative idea	Team head	Quarterly	By selecting the best business idea	By putting winner's photograph on star intranet and recognizing him/her on star intranet
3	Selling star award	Award given to sales people	Sales manager	Monthly	By selecting a person who achieve the highest target	Gift voucher, free lunch
4	Attendance award	Given for highest attendance	Team head	Monthly	By keeping a digital system for attendance	Certificate, cash bonus
5	Leadership Award	Given for leadership skills	HR manager	Monthly	Recognize excellent leadership demonstration	Recognise the employee during monthly staff meetings with a certificate
6	Hall of Fame	Rewarding the right behaviour as per our value system	Manager	Monthly	By recognizing superlative performance	By putting the employee name and photograph on star intranet
7	Note of thanks	Saying thanks to employees for doing some extraordinary work	HR manager	On going	By recognizing small acts of kindness/help/teamwork	Email thanks or thank you card

Table-5 Recommendations for better reward and recognitions.

After collecting the 80 questionnaires were distributed among the employees out of whom 65 were responded appropriately giving an 85% response which is acceptable to make this study rigorous

and generalizable. The obtained data is analyzed through Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 16. The statistical methods involved those of descriptive (mean and standard deviation) and inferential statistics (Pearson Correlation) for the predictors of motivation and satisfaction of employees. The perimeter of study starts with payment, working condition, promotion, benefits etc. But few more activities they can start in their organization for better reward and recognition of employees.

7. CONCLUSION OF THE STUDY:

The presentation of results achieved in this study. Pearson's product moment correlation was used to indicate relationships and differences in the dimensions of work motivation and satisfaction based on the sample used in the study and more specifically to indicate differences in rewards and recognition (as components within the work satisfaction and motivation questionnaire). The results in reflect that there is a statistically significant relationship between reward and recognition respectively, and motivation and satisfaction. The study revealed that if rewards or recognition offered to employees were to be altered, then there would be a corresponding change in work motivation and satisfaction. The results of this study also indicated that employees were less motivated by rewards and recognition than some of the other dimensions of the Work Satisfaction and Motivation Questionnaire. By implication, this means that if more focus is placed on rewards and recognition, it could have a resultant positive impact on motivation and thus result in higher levels of job performance. As per the findings of the survey the monetary as well as the non-monetary awards both are equally important but the main aim is to reward or recognize employees time to time. The recognitions like congratulatory cards, wall of fame, public applause and public recognition is of greater importance. Performance should be considered criterion for rewarding. There should be rewards or recognitions such that the employee can get to celebrated the reward with his family members as well. The get together or parties within the branch, such that the employees get to interact and communicate with their colleagues, is of great importance. The managers should make sure that he has one-to-one interactions with their employees and colleagues. The rewarding system should be such that the reward being given to employee means something to him/her, i.e. the reward should have meaning for the recipient. Rewards should always be achievable and not out of reach by employees. These rewards should be used as reward

for their extra effort and it has to other than the incentives/bonus, which gets added to their salary. Rewards should be visible to all the employees.

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